

*a non-profit
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*Thormøhlensgate 47,
N-5006 Bergen
Norway*

NERSC Technical Report no. 288

MARCOAST
SERVICE PROVIDER VALIDATION REPORT:
WATER QUALITY MONITORING OF THE NORTH SEA,
KATTEGAT AND SKAGERRAK
AND
HAB DETECTION, ALERT AND FORECASTING FOR
NORWEGIAN WATERS

by

**Lasse Pettersson, Knut-Frode Dagestad,
Sonia Christina (NERSC)
Kai Sørensen (NIVA),
Gunnar S. Larsen (FD),
Kjell Maroni (FHL)**

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Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center

Thormøhlensgate 47

N-5006 Bergen - NORWAY

Phone: +47 55 20 58 00 Fax. +47 55 20 58 01

E-mail: administrasjon@nersc.noWeb.site: <http://www.nersc.no>

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MARINE AND COASTAL ENVIRONMENTAL INFORMATION SERVICES

MarCoast Service Provider Validation Report:
*S3: Water quality monitoring of the North Sea,
 Kattegat and Skagerrak*
*S4: HAB detection, alert and forecasting for
 Norwegian waters*
Deliverable No. C6

	Name	Responsibility
Prepared by	Lasse H. Pettersson, NERSC	NERSC project manager
Contributions from	Knut-Frode Dagestad, NERSC Kai Sørensen, NIVA Sonia Christina, NERSC Gunnar S. Larsen, FD Kjell Maroni, FHL	Project scientists Service User

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CHANGE RECORDS

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Abbreviations

C5	MarCoast Service Validation Protocol compiled by MarCoast Validation Bureau
C6	Validation Report, compiled by MarCoast Validation Bureau with major contributions of Service Providers and Core Users
MSVP	MarCoast Service Validation Protocol
SPVR	Service Provider Validation Report
VBVR	Validation Bureau Validation Report
SPS	Service Portfolio Specification
HAB	Harmful Algae Bloom
WQ	Water quality
NERSC	Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center
SLA	Service Level Agreement

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Service provider Validation and Verification activities

This chapter describes the validation and verification activities performed by the service provider. The following requirements, which are described in the MarCoast Service Validation Protocol (MSVP, deliverable C5), should be taken into account:

1. **General Quality Criteria** (defined in MSVP chapter 3)
2. **Verification and validation criteria** for MarCoast Services and Products (defined in MSVP chapter 4)
3. **Guideline for the Validation & Verification activities** to be performed by the Service Provider (See chapters 6.1 and 6.2 in MSVP)

In order to facilitate the work, the structure of the following chapter follows the structure of chapter 6.2 found within the MSVP.

SERVICES; S3: “WATER QUALITY MONITORING OF THE NORTH SEA, KATTEGAT AND SKAGERRAK” AND S4: “HAB DETECTION, ALERT AND FORECASTING FOR NORWEGIAN WATERS”

Service and product description; V&V basis ¹

Service and product name

The NERSC MarCoast services performed under S3 are named “[Water quality monitoring of the North Sea, Kattegat and Skagerrak](#)” (WP 3350) and under S4 are “[HAB detection, alert and forecasting for Norwegian waters](#)” (WP3430). Both services provides information map products and assessment reports based on MERIS data, covering the EO products for distribution of (i) chlorophyll-a, (ii) true colour (RGB) image and (iii) sea surface temperature (SST) for the Norwegian and adjacent coastal waters (the extended North Sea area). For the S3 service additionally EO products provided are (iv) the total suspended matter and (v) the dissolved organic matter, primarily used for water quality monitoring. Also the temporal monthly averaged products are used more in S3 than in S4. These MarCoast Services are complementary to activities initiated under the Norwegian SatOcean program funded by the Norwegian Space Centre.

Service and product functional description

A production line for EO data acquisition, processing, products generation, and dissemination (at <http://HAB.nersc.no>) for both of the MarCoast services has been implemented. The satellite based information are being ingested into the service in near real-time on “daily” basis. The products are generated according to the specific processing chain for our service as illustrated in *Figure 1*. This includes three major tasks;

1. Access to and acquisition of Envisat MERIS (and MODIS) Level-2 data products

¹ Since some of these issues are already described within other documents, such as the SLA, the production plan and the SPS, the validation report may cite the relevant parts of these documents, which are related to the respective product.

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2. Service production line for generation of Processed products and Statistical data binning
3. Data Integration, Analysis/Assessment, Visualization and Dissemination

	Steps	Data format	Shell script
Download	MERIS on ESA ftp (Rolling archives / ACRI - tdb)	N1	Launch scripts for the various steps
	Data download		
	MERIS on NERSC server	N1	
Processing	Map re-projection - BEAM		
	MERIS	DIM	
	NERSC algorithm (BOREALI) processing		
	MERIS	DIM +IMG	
	Post-processing (Matlab)		
Visualisation	Concentration distribution maps + transect extracts (daily, weekly, monthly)	JPG TIFF PNG	
	Web visualisation (php)		
	Data on the screen for end user	HTML Google KML	

Figure 1 The NERSC processing chain for generation of various MERIS based ocean products for use in near real-time or off-line applications for the NERSC MarCoast services under S3 and S4.

The service production chain for the information products is based on near real-time access to the ESA MERIS rolling archive in Kiruna. The rolling archive is daily and automatically checked for new relevant EO data updates within the geographical area of operation for the service and accordingly new processed MERIS data are down-loaded when they become available. The downloaded data are the standard MERIS Level-2 data, which are locally stored at NERSC for further processing and products generation.

The MERIS based derived EO products are based on both standard ESA algorithms (Level-2 products) as well as a regionally tuned algorithm for Norwegian coastal waters. Binned Level-3 products are generated as a part of the service for all products with daily updates for respectively (i) the daily image composites (from one or two passes per day) as well as (ii) 7-days average products. The (iii) monthly binned EO products are updated every month. For each parameter the products are generated with a fixed scale bar, which allows direct comparison of time evolution for each parameter in consecutive images.

The standard (Level-2) ESA MERIS chlorophyll-a products² for respectively Case-1 and -2 waters (algal_1 and algal_2), total suspended matter (total_susp) and CDOM (yellow_subs) are extracted from each satellite pass covering fully or partly the geographical area monitored by the service. Level-3 products are generated for use in the service. Additionally an RGB true-colour image composite is generated from the MERIS spectral channels 2, 5 and 6. A

² ATBDs are found at <http://envisat.esa.int/instruments/meris/atbd/>

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regional “in-house” developed algorithm (NERSC/NIERSC see e.g. Pozdnyakov et al, 2005³) is used for retrieval of a set of regional specific data products for the above listed bio-geophysical parameters (chlorophyll-a, total suspended matter, CDOM as well as an error assessment).

Sea surface temperature (SST) products are generated from MODIS data obtained from a NASA ftp-site. Binned Level-3 products are generated.

All above EO data products (ESA and “in-house” regional algorithms) (see *Table 1*) are generated in jpg (web-use), GeoTIFF (for web-map servers) and Google Earth (KML) image formats, as well as MatLab data files and placed on the project-web for analysis, assessment as well as further dissemination to the users. All formats meet the users requirements and following agreed protocols for their further use of the data.

Products name	Product	Algorithm	File key name	Service S3/S4
chl case 1 ESA	Chlorophyll-a	ESA (case 1)	algal_1	Both
chl case II ESA	Chlorophyll-a	ESA (case 2)	algal_2	Both
tsm ESA	Total Suspended Matter	ESA	total_susp	S3
cdom ESA	Coloured Dissolved Organic Matter	ESA	yellow_subs	S3
chl NERSC/NIERSC	Chlorophyll-a	NERSC/NIERSC	lmchl	Both
tsm NERSC/NIERSC	Total Suspended Matter	NERSC/NIERSC	lmsm	S3
cdom NERSC/NIERSC	Coloured Dissolved Organic Matter	NERSC/NIERSC	lmdoc	S3
mse NERSC/NIERSC	Mean square error (difference between measured and reconstructed Rrsw spectra, also used as retrieval quality estimation)	NERSC/NIERSC	mse	Both
counts NERSC/NIERSC	Number of pixels used in the averaging	NERSC/NIERSC	counts	Both
RGB NERSC/NIERSC	Pseudo colour image constructed from 2 nd (442 nm), 5 th (559 nm) and 6 th (619) MERIS bands.	NERSC/NIERSC	rgb	Both
SST MODIS	Sea surface temperature from MODIS	NASA	sst	Both

Table 1: A summary of the MarCoast products generated, their basis and the output parameters identification. The main service applications (S3 or S4) are indicated, but not being exclusive. All products are generated daily, and binned in 1-day, 7-days running averages and binned monthly per calendar month.

In order to increase the availability of applicable of data - mainly due to cloud cover limitations of optical EO data - a seven-days running mean data product is generated every day for all information products. The effects of regional or local cloud cover in the individual images are accordingly reduced at the expense of smoothening some of the signal in the peak high values of the mapped parameters. Monthly mean products are also made at the end of each calendar month and disseminated on the web. For visualisation, analysis and own assessment of the data, the project website allows interactive user selection among the above information parameters, algorithms and binning periods (together products) can be done by entering the specified time-intervals and a sub-selection among the different EO information products (see header in *Figure 2*).

³ Pozdnyakov D.V, A.A. Korosov, H. Grassl and L.H. Pettersson, 2005: An advanced algorithm for operational retrieval of water quality parameters from satellite data in the visible. Int. J. Remote Sensing, Vol 26, no 12, pp. 2669-2687, DOI:10.1080/014311160500044697

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Figure 2: Screen dump of a selection of 1-day and 7-days binned information products for a 3-days period in May 2006. Here shown is the ESA chlorophyll-a case 1 (algal_1), the NERSC/NIERSC Chl-a (lmchl) and the MODIS SST (sst) products, delivered under both MarCoast services S3 and S4. The image examples are binned for respectively 1-day and 7-days periods. The user can interactively select the information products, their binning period (1-, 7-days or monthly) and time period for display. Here the data are shown for the baseline MarCoast SLA-agreed area of coverage i.e. “the North Sea”. The user can download the images in GeoTIFF, KML for Google or MatLab (password access) formats for own further processing. Some additional geographical areas of coverage have been introduced during 2006.

Availability and reliability targets

Daily updates of the provided EO based map products (Level-3) should according to agreement be available within 24 hours after the satellite pass. Typically the products are available during the same late afternoon (4-8 hours after acquisition) every day. Daily and seven-days average products are generated each day and the 30 days average products are made every month and posted on the website.

Performance measures

The SLA users performance measures are based on the timely and regular availability of EO data products during the algae bloom season. Ultimately, the performance is assessed through the ability of the service to identify specific harmful algae bloom events or water quality

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anomalies in Norwegian waters, being of concern to the aquaculture industry or authorities. Environmental limitations in EO data capabilities (e.g. cloud cover, no detection of layer blooms) and lack of satellite data due to mission anomalies are outside the control of the service.

Accessibility: Open source; Public domain; Proprietary; Licensed

The information products are distributed in the public domain at <http://HAB.nersc.no>. Only the MatLab files, to be used further processing, are restricted in use by a password protection. Our two MarCoast SLA users also disseminate the latest information products as well as provide a link to the MarCoast service site through their own website, respectively;

- the “Emergency portal of the Directorate of Fisheries” at http://www.fiskeridir.no/fiskeridir/fiskeridirektoratets_beredskapsportal,
- the national fisheries portal of the Ministry of Fisheries at http://www.fisheries.no/aquaculture/environment/environment_pollution/aquaculture_environment_pollution.htm and through
- the public website of the Norwegian Sea Food Federation at <http://www.fhl.no/>.

External Interfaces

MERIS Level-2 data are downloaded daily from the ESA Envisat rolling archives at <https://oa-ks.eo.esa.int/ra/> (Kiruna Rolling Archive) and the MODIS data at <ftp://oceans.gsfc.nasa.gov/subscriptions/375/> (NASA subscription ftp-server). These EO data are stored at NERSC server and processed further for generation of the service Level-2 and Level-3 products.

The EO products generated by the service are fetched from NERSC ftp-server for use at the external to NERSC dissemination sites, as well as these external sites provides a link back to the NERSC service site (<http://HAB.nersc.no>).

An ftp-link is also established for transfer of various GeoTIFF image products to Norwegian Institute for Waters Research (NIVA) and for use in the Norwegian Space Centre/NIVA SatOcean Web Map Server (WMS) portal as well as preparing for integration of Ferrybox data during the Phase 2 Extension of the MarCoast Service. Met.no also receives GeoTIFF products for use at <http://wms.met.no/moncoze>.

Operations pre-requisites (manpower, operational environment)

The Service processing chain (Figure 1) is done in a computer environment based on a RedHat Linux operating system running on two dual core AMD Opteron 2.0 Ghz processors with 9 GB of RAM. Software used is Matlab, Python and C++.

All routines for down-load, processing and posting data on the web are automated using scripts that at regular time intervals check for relevant (covering the study area) and updated MERIS L-2 data from the ESA Envisat rolling archives.

The performance of the automatic operations are monitored daily, during regularly work hours - five days per week. In case products are not generated or posted on the web-dissemination system, the cause and problems are solved by manual re-initialisation of the processing routines and/or solving other mal-functions of the system.

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During regular operations the service products are assessed once per day, mainly during regular working hours, but also during weekends in case of critical bloom periods. Assessment reports can be posted on the service website using a password-protected function (available to the service provider) and a web-browser. The service analysis and assessment can accordingly be maintained using a regular “low speed” internet connection. During alert bloom situations, the performance of the system and data interpretation is done more frequently. The users also report eventual anomalies in the service provision directly to NERSC, after which maintenance actions are initiated. NERSC also takes part in the national emergency team to be established by the Directorate of Fisheries in case of special alert events.

User requirements

During the main algae growth season, typically February to October, the SLA users requires daily updates of the generated EO based products, using the various algorithms and binning periods implemented (see above), in order to do their own assessment of the algae bloom situation in Norwegian coastal waters. Their assessment is based on the MarCoast service information as well as their own auxiliary *in situ* observations and experience. The capability of the EO data to also provide information about geographical areas offshore the regular network of coastal stations is important. This includes also the up-stream waters of the North Sea, Skagerrak and Kattegat. The NERSC MarCoast service provider also performs assessment of the algae blooms situation based on our EO products and other available information. If potential harmful or major algae bloom events are developing or identified direct mail to about 40 key individual users in Norway, Sweden, Denmark and Scotland are initiated. The users may then initiate their own measures to get additional regional information and make their further assessment and actions.

Technical documentation

The service has been set up for daily updates with near real-time operations from 1st February 2006. The status for the 2006 service provision cover the period up to mid October 2006, when the major algae growth season was over. Routines for generation, dissemination and analysis of information products have been developed, implemented, tested and operated for all agreed EO-based HAB-monitoring (S4) and water quality service (S3) products. A total of 17.500 graphical products have been generated since the start of the MarCoast service at <http://HAB.nersc.no>. This number is fare above the number agreed in the production plan. During the period of major high biomass algae blooming (typically March to September) the site have been monitored near daily (at a minimum during the five working days per week), assessed and the EO data products analysed by NERSC experts. Upon identification of particular events (typically abrupt changes or extreme values of chlorophyll-a distribution or in the RBG-reflectance and/or in the SST) e-mail alert notices have been generated, describing the phenomenon and sent to about 40 selected core users in Norway, Sweden, Denmark and Scotland. The same information has also been posted on the service website (see Figure 3). *In situ* measurements and mitigation actions have accordingly been initiated and in some cases reported back to NERSC. However, the aquaculture authorities or industry

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did **not** identify any major potential or real HAB-event during 2006 of such extent that the dedicated emergency plan came into force.

Figure 3: An example of the home page (<http://HAB.nersc.no>) posted at the NERSC MarCoast services.

Technology Assessment, Failure Mode Identification and Risk Ranking

Predictability in the regular supply of updated EO data from the data supply sources (space agencies) is essential, both in a stable format and quality of delivered data products as well as timely delivery of the data. The MERIS rolling archives and MODIS ftp-supply used seems in most cases to meet these requirements. Some delays and no-delivery of data are identified. Internal automatic routines for operator alerts in case of failure in the NERSC processing chain should be improved. Currently these are mainly identified through lack of data available at the service front-end website.

Otherwise the established processing system capacity is sufficient, however design issues in the presentation and particular the integration of various information products can and will be improved.

After the initial test and evaluation phase, the following major anomalies have occurred in 2006 due to;

1. **Local disk capacity overflow and system changes;** During two events in 2006 (August 8th to 14th and August 28th) major revisions of the NERSC computer and disk systems have caused delay in the availability and processing of data for the MarCoast Service. The malfunction has been corrected and data processed at a later time, with delay up to six days (during a vacation period).
2. **Delays in the NRT ESA Level-2 processing;** The length of the Level-2 MERIS segments available at the rolling archive ftp-server has in periods to be shorter and appears in periods at a later time later than is expected regular mode. Short segments and delayed

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delivery cause problems for the service to both meet the quality (lack in area covered) and delivery time of the scheduled products.

3. **Lack of availability of MERIS data;** For totally of 10 days during the period of operations in 2006 (totally 289 days of operations) MERIS data has not been available from Envisat, mainly due to abrupt or scheduled satellite anomalies. All anomalies have been reported by ESA EOHelp and information forwarded to our service users.
4. **Change of the ESA MERIS data format;** On 8th May ESA changed the MERIS processing version for the rolling archive. This included changes in the data format, which needed to be corrected for in our automatic processing routines, with an accordingly interruption and delay in the service provision.

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No.	Failure Description	Reason	Probability [%] or low/moderate/high	Matter of risk	Probability [%] or low/moderate/high
1	Technical errors @ service provider.	H/W or S/W errors or malfunctions	Low	Delay of updated products (up to 6 days).	Low
2	Delay in input data.	Satellite or ground segment anomalies.	Low	Delay in new products.	Low
3	Lack of EO data.	Satellite or ground segment anomalies.	Low (3.5% - 10 days)	Lack of updated products.	Low
4	Change in EO data format.	Ground segment algorithm change.	Low (once)	Delay in updated products.	Low
5	Cloud cover ⁴ .	Weather	Moderate to high	No useful parameter values	Low to Moderate (some algae blooms tend to be correlated to high pressure systems).

Table 2: Overview about failures and risks related to service quality and delivery.

Concept Improvement

The MarCoast service implementation started with severe under-capacity of local disk-space storage available at NERSC, however this has been improved through an upgrade of the NERSC disk system and installation of three new disks with total 1,5 Tb storage capacity (for both MarCoast and other use). Disk capacity was not a problem during the latter part of the operations in 2006.

⁴ An environmental limitation of optical EO data, with strong seasonal temporal variability.

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The server used at NERSC used to maintain the MarCoast front-end service and other web-based services at NERSC, are also due for up-grade and replacement. This will be done in 2007.

Management plan

The NERSC MarCoast project manger has the overall responsibility for the service operations and its regular assessment. In his absence other senior staff at NERSC are allocated to the service management. The functions of web-interface to perform the service assessment and reporting have also been used external from the NERSC offices.

The system development has been performed as well maintained mainly by two scientific and technical staff at NERSC. They have improved and maintained the service functions in case of technical malfunctions and errors. The IT-manager also knows of the general processing scheme and functions needed to operate and maintain the service functions.

Evaluation of the Probability of Success

Since **no** major HAB event has been identified in 2006 the major service benefit has been on its capability to early identify potential blooms and accordingly initiate dedicated *in situ* observations at specific locations in order to optimise the sampling for these areas. The service SLA users have regularly used and assessed the service an products provided (see e.g. Annex 1).

The service use and attention has also increased, illustrated by the fact that more than 2500 different users have accessed the service website site, with a core of between 8 and 20 regular “daily” users from both aquaculture and fisheries industry and authorities.

The service benefit has been demonstrated in supplement to, and not as a replacement of, the *in situ* based algae monitoring activities in Norway - AlgeInfo published at <http://algeinfo.imr.no>. The synergetic use is essential for the overall efficiency of an integrated monitoring of algae blooms in coastal waters. Several of the experts contributing to the weekly update of AlgeInfo are regular users of the MarCoast service.

Validation Activities

Validation Plan

During Phase 1 a limited amount of *in situ* data were regularly available to the MarCoast service operations. A more extensive validation is accordingly planned for Phase 2 extension, where Ferrybox data from NIVA (Kai Sørensen and Dominique Durand) will be integrated to the service on a regular basis.

The service validation and assessment activities undertaken during MarCoast Phase 1 in 2006, includes;

1. Comparison of EO based products (i.e. the different Chl-*a* products) with Ferrybox data.
2. Comparison between satellite EO data products and ecosystem model simulations.
3. Non-SLA users statements of service performance and quality.

Validation

1. Comparison of EO based products with Ferrybox data

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A comparison of the MarCoast Service EO Chlorophyll-*a* products (algal_1, algal_2 and lmchl) belonging to both services S3 and S4 and the NIVA Ferrybox chlorophyll fluorescence data⁵ has been performed for the period of May 2006. These data are provided through the Norwegian SatOcean programme, within a project coordinated by NIVA. **The *in situ* data used in this validation is based on the Chlorophyll-*a* fluorescence not converted to Chl-*a* based on water samples. It should be clearly noted that the *in situ* data only give relative values and relative errors. An absolute validation of the EO products will be performed later!** For these reasons regressions analysis will not demonstrate the full quality of the service and data products. The Ferrybox system makes daily ship transects between Oslo, Norway and Fredrikshavn in Denmark (Figure 4). The cloud free satellite EO data products were extracted along the ferry line transect. Matching data in time and space from both the Ferrybox and the satellite were acquired and analysed.

SST data derived from MODIS has been validated extensively and for the service application purposes the relative accuracy of 0.1°K is sufficient, while the absolute values are not that critical.

Figure 4: The NIVA Ferrybox transect between Oslo and Fredrikshavn.

For each of the three EO based chlorophyll products match up in space and time (up to 12 hours difference) has been analysed along the Ferrybox transect (summarized in Figure 5). Since this preliminary validation was based on uncorrected and uncalibrated Chl-*a* fluorescence data only the relative difference between the EO products can be analysed. We see that the relative difference between Algal_1 and Algal-2 are less that 0.5 mg/m³ in the central and open Skagerrak (58-58.5). The lmchl products are significant lower (approx 1 mg/m³). Close to the coast of Denmark (57.5) it is difficult to use the data due to land effects, and in the vicinity of the Norwegian coast (59.0) where both particles and CDOM increases the EO products fail and specially Algal_1 and Algal_2. In the Inner Oslofjord (>59.5) all the products show the same magnitude of relative error.

Conclusive statements on the absolute quality of the three assessed algorithms for Chlorophyll-*a* retrieval from MERIS data are not possible based on the present data of comparison.

⁵ Sorensen K, (2006). Ferrybox- From Online Oceanographic Observations to Environmental information. Report on the use of ferrybox data for validation purposes of satellite data. Deliverable D-5-4 Ferrybox contract EVK2-2002-0014.

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Figure 5: MarCoast service EO products (in blue) for chlorophyll-a distribution plotted along the Ferrybox transect between Fredrikshavn (left) and Oslo (right) for (a) the ESA **algal_1** product, (b) the **algal_2** product and (c) the **lmchl** product during the month of May 2006. The in situ chlorophyll fluorescence values (in relative unit due to not exact calibration of the in situ data) are provide by NIVA (Sørensen, pers. comm.) and plotted in red. (d) The mean relative difference between the EO and in situ chlorophyll-a fluorescence relative values are shown for respectively **algal_1**, **algal_2** and **lmchl**.

The value of comparing Ferrybox data in real time with the EO products are clearly shown in Figure 6 where the MERIS Algal_1 product (7-days average) are overlaid with the Chl-a fluorescence data from two transect form the ferry Princess of Norway operating between Bergen and Newcastle. Data from the spring bloom of 2006.

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Figure 6: a) Shows the Chl-a fluorescence data from the sensor on the ship along the route from Stavanger to Bergen. b) The overlaid MERIS Algal_1 product with the ship data from the ferry. Data from the SatOcean project (Sørensen, pers. comm. presented at Envisat 2007).

2. Comparison between satellite EO data products and ecosystem model simulations

The Institute of Marine Research has developed and operates the NORWECOM model for simulations of the concentrations phytoplankton, i.e. diatoms and flagellates, in southern Norwegian coastal waters. The model is implemented with a 4 km spatial resolution and provides daily (every 6 hour) forecasts of a range of geo-bio-chemical ocean state variables (totally 15 parameters). The model is used in the predictions of the development and decay of algae blooms and can be reinitialised during special bloom events. The fact that the model performance has increased robustness also including the biological part implies that it is useful to assess the algae situation and its development. Following the now completed Norwegian MONCOZE project the modelled results and satellite products from NERSC are made available at <http://wms.met.no/moncoze> for integrated use.

Several events of modelling of high biomass phytoplankton blooms are well coinciding in time and space with the observations from the MarCoast EO data (see Figure 7 and 5), however also events of algae blooms observed in the satellite data are not predicted in the model and on some occasions also visa versa. The ability to detect and to predict algae blooms is clearly pending on the location, timing, intensity and type of algae bloom. The model also provides information during periods when cloud cover limits the applicability of the satellite EO information and there are complementary in use.

Figure 7: An example of a MarCoast service satellite detected algae blooms (left) and modelled phytoplankton (right) in coastal waters on August 1st 2005. Model data from <http://wms.met.no/moncoze>.

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Figure 8: An example of a MarCoast service satellite detected algae blooms (left) and modelled phytoplankton (right) in coastal waters on March 27th 2007. Model data from <http://wms.met.no/moncoze>.

3. Non-SLA users statements of service performance and quality

Encouraging e-mail responses about the service performance have been received from service users in addition to the core SLA users (see also the SLA users assessment in Ch. 2);

- Leading scientist Dr. Karl Tangen, SINTEF Aquaculture and Fisheries, Trondheim, Norway; “We are continuously monitoring your service and find the satellite images useful and a quite high correlation with our *in situ* observations, at least during high pressure situations with little cloud cover.” (translated from an e-mail in Norwegian language).
- Prof. Geir Johnsen, Trondheim Biological station, University of Trondheim, Norway: “The operational remote sensing of phytoplankton blooms, coloured dissolved organic matter and total suspended matter along the Norwegian coast from HAB-NERSC is of outmost importance for harmful algae monitoring in Norway/Scandinavia. The data provided, also implemented also in Google Earth, is the current state-of-the-art for governmental decision making, general monitoring, understanding of plankton and water mass dynamics for both applied and basic science. Together with the Norwegian observation network, providing water samples for HAB species and the Norwegian food authority (Mattilsynet) providing phytoplankton toxicity tests in mussels along the Norwegian coast line, the NERSC-HAB monitoring service is world leading in operational phytoplankton monitoring. Internationally, HAB monitoring is hot topic and NERSC (Lasse Pettersson) was asked to write a chapter in the new 3rd edition of the highly known and used UNESCO-book "Pigments in Oceanography". At present, the international editorial committee of the book (Roy, Johnsen, Egeland, Llewellyn and Wright) regard NERSC among the world leaders of operational remote sensing of phytoplankton blooms.” (copied from an e-mail).

Validation Assessment

With the available data (*in situ* and EO) from 2006 and resources a comprehensive validation of each of the service products cannot be performed. However, the validation exercise, model comparison and users statements clearly indicate that the MarCoast Service is “fit for users purpose”. The users and other obtains EO based information products in order to early detect and monitor the development and decay of potential high biomass algae blooms in coastal waters. The temporal binning of the EO data products also improves their applicability through reduction of the impact of cloud cover, however at the expense of smoothing the signal of eventual peak bloom events.

Concerning the validation of Chl-*a* products some general statements are possible, which are essential for our users in order to perform their assessment and use of the information from the EO data products provided by our MarCoast services:

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- The ESA **Algal_2** product seems to match the *in situ* observations best in the central Skagerrak region. This is not surprising since several *in situ* data from this region have been used to tune this algorithm.
- The ESA **Algal_1** is likewise overestimating the chl-a concentration, while the NERSC **lmschl** gives and underestimate compared to the *in situ* data for the same region.
- All Chl-*a* algorithms give (some significantly) overestimates the Chl-*a* concentration in the entrance of the turbid Oslofjord and gives underestimate within the fjord area. The lmschl product seems to be more accurate in fjord entrance region, but still gives a significant under estimate within the Oslofjord.
- The absolute values of the various Chl-*a* products should accordingly be used with precaution in the assessment of phytoplankton concentrations.
- In coastal areas, not under direct influence of river such as Glomma (outer Oslofjord), one may accordingly use the relative differences (spatial and to some extent temporal) in the Chlorophyll-*a* products with good confidentiality.
- The quality of the atmospheric correction are strongly pending on the actual conditions during the satellite pass and day-to-day differences may be significant.

The periods of high probability of extensive algae blooms are also often consistent with periods of high pressure weather systems with “nice and sunny” conditions, which makes the optical EO data more applicable. The fact that no major harmful algae bloom happened in Norwegian waters during 2006, causing losses to the aquaculture industry, do not reduce the applicability of the service for the authorities and industry who needs to be on alert and to optimize their dedicated field data sampling.

The service EO products also expand the actual area monitored to those up stream of the Norwegian interest (following the general ocean circulation pattern), which accordingly can be advected into waters of concern to our users. The service information is complementary to the very extensive national *in situ* monitoring activities (AlgeInfo stations and Ferrybox systems) available for Norwegian waters. Also users outside the prime geographical area find benefit in the use of the service and Danish and Swedish users regularly visit the project website.

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User verification and validation activities

USER QUESTIONNAIRE – NORWEGIAN DIRECTORATE OF FISHERIES (FD)

The core user(s) of the product(s) is (are) requested to fill out the User Questionnaire defined in the MSVP. The answers should be given as comments where appropriate. Please refer to chapter 7 of the MSVP (C5) before answering the questions.

In case, that the core user(s) will provide further contributions to the validation and verification, the results should be described at the end of the corresponding chapter (0, 0, 0) as general comments.

The questions to the core user(s) that contributed to V&V activities are grouped according to the following topics:

1. User requirements
2. Technical requirements
3. Validation

User requirements – FD

The below questionnaire is completed by Gunnar S. Larsen, FD, through a phone interview with Lasse H. Pettersson (partly in Norwegian and then translated). The final text has been approved by the user. A general letter of statement from the user is given in the Annex 1 to this report.

1. Does the end-user have effective access to the delivered information?

Yes, the information is available through the web, which we access daily during the algae growth season and through direct e-mail warning from NERSC.

2. Is there effective communication between service provider and end-user including effective feedback mechanisms?

Particularly during identified “special bloom events” and during start up or changes in the service.

3. Is the presentation of information effective and suitable to the end user requirements?

Yes, complementary to other information about the bloom activity available to FD.

4. What user needs does the service meet/not meet?

MEET: The NERSC service provides the information FD needs concerning early detection of high biomass blooms, including other oceanographic information, which are supplementary to our own information sources and measurements. Together this gives us a better picture of the overall bloom situation at any time.

NOT MEET: The service does not provide information about deep layer and low biomass toxic blooms, but this is a known limitation of these data. Cloud cover is limiting our use, but the 7days products improve our use.

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5. *To which international policies and regional directives, treaties and agreements does the services product(s) refer?*

The service is primary meeting our **national** requirements and responsibility defined by the Norwegian Ministry of Fisheries and Coastal Affairs. FD have the overall responsibility for monitoring and handling of emergency situations related to the algae blooms etc. in the Norwegian coastal zone.

FD does not have a major national responsibility vs. the Water Framework Directive, but the service applicability may be limited by the 1 nautical mile area extent of the WFD.

6. *Does the service provide useful information for monitoring and assessing the state of the marine environment? Is there an added value brought by the service (i.e. is there a benefit or not – e. g. cost reduction, spatial/temporal coverage).*

Yes, the service provides us with early information about possible algae bloom events, which are essential for our information to the Ministry and to the aquaculture industry, who can then initiate mitigation actions to save values and reduce their losses. The information is also used to initiate dedicated field observations improving our own monitoring, integration with ferrybox data and a better and more optimal sampling of *in situ* data can be assured. Both the temporal and spatial coverage are better than can be provided through other observations.

7. *(Optional) General comments regarding user requirements.*

Several stakeholders from industry, consultancy, research and authorities contribute to the monitoring of Norwegian waters, however there is no unified system for handling and integrating the information from all sources. The implementation of such an integrated system is hampered by the lack of public initiative as well as the proprietary and commercial rights to some of the data used in the algae monitoring.

Technical requirements - FD

1. *Does the service provide timely, reliable, and relevant information?*

Yes indeed very much.

2. *What are the shortcomings and how often do they occur?*

Failure or significant delays in EO data products delivery has occurred, but only a few times during 2006 (as reported by NERSC in Ch. 1.1.3).

3. *Are the shortcomings of the service explained?*

We are often informed in the web-comments text area or through direct e-mail explaining the reason for the delay or lack of updated EO products or other errors.

4. *Are uncertainties in the service products addressed in the documentation?*

To some extent, however as a long-term service user since 1998, we are well aware of the shortcomings and limitations of the products, but learned to appreciate their availability and useful applications of the service.

5. *Are the conditions under which the service is provided clearly identified?*

Yes, through the agreement (SLA) and direct contacts with NERSC.

6. *Are the service products documented in a complete and transparent manner?*

Yes, needed information has been supplied to us as an experienced user. Technical information about the products is available on the web too.

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7. *Is the product format and volume compliant with the specifications?*

Format of products are delivered as jointly agreed and requested. For automatic delivery of data to our FD website this has been agreed between the technical staff. Some products have been developed and are now delivered as a result of a dialogue with NERSC, e.g. the 7 days time averaged products. More useful products are delivered than initially agreed.

8. *Are the service's spatial (geographical) and temporal boundaries clearly defined?*

Oh yes. We would like to have the entire Norwegian waters covered by the service (*Comment LHP*: This is a part of the activities planned for Phase 2 Extension).

9. *(Optional) Does the service make use of appropriate local/regional information which may improve the final product(s)?*

This is mainly integrated in our assessment as the user.

10. *(Optional) Have the algorithms been tuned to local conditions (where necessary)?*

Yes, in addition to the standard algorithms also regional products is provided. Which product is the best is pending on the geographical area and the period of observations. We assess the information together.

11. *(Optional) Are the quality control procedures (e.g. flags) used appropriately?*

Yes, but the flags are not explicitly visible to us. We do also do our own screening of the quality of the data, which are both pending on the environmental conditions and the time of the year and area.

12. *(Optional) Have conservative assumptions been used?*

Together with our own assessment of the data quality, yes.

13. *Did any cases of disruption or temporary service non-compliance occur? If yes, how often?*

Technical delay or complete lack of updated satellite data has occurred only a few times during 2006 – for reasons as explained by NERSC in Section 1.1.3. Additionally some events of delays in providing updated satellite images (up to a few days) have occurred. Cloud cover has been the main reason for lack of useful information from the service.

14. *What are the user risks related to disruption or temporary service non-compliance?*

Through regular use we maintain a good picture of the development of the situation. Also other information sources keep informed. Accordingly it is not critical if data are not available daily, however lacking data from one cloud free day in a critical period is not optimal. The service information has been used several times to initiate dedicated field observations – saving both time and resources for our sampling.

15. *Is the authority and responsibility of the service delivery management clearly described?*

Yes, in “Beredskapsplanen” is the responsibility and tasks well defined. During an alert situation the responsibility and contributions of NERSC are more comprehensive than during the regular service. Regional/local interpretation and graphics are made as well as presenting these to the media. Our experience is that NERSC provides all what is needed during such events.

16. *(Optional) Does the service require extensive initial training efforts in order to work as presumed during the service delivery period?*

No, however as a user during several years and through our cooperation with NERSC we have built up our own experience to make use of the service and products.

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17. (Optional) Does the service make provisions for meeting training needs?

Earlier in our cooperation (prior to MarCoast) we had technical training meetings. Now we have informal meeting and suggestions for improvements of the service is made through feed-back from us.

18. (Optional) Is a mechanism in place to assess the impact of the training and promotion activities?

Partly, though our “promotion” and link back to the NERSC website at our “Berdsksportalen” and the Norwegian fisheries web site (*Comment LHP*: I assume these links would have been removed if no benefit was found).

19. (Optional) Are procedures identified to rapidly alert authorities in emergency situations?

Defiantly, YES!!! In our “Varslingsplan for Fiskridirektoratet ved krisehåndtering i kystsonen” (*Comment LHP*: translates to “Emergency plan for the coastal zone”) the Nansen Centre is listed as remote sensing expertise institution/staff to be called upon in case of emergency events. The key persons to be notified within and external to FD are included in this plan. Several of these are also included in the NERSC e-mail list used in case of identification of “special bloom events”. FD has the responsibility to further inform and initiate actions/alert modes as described in the plan.

20. (Optional) General comments regarding technical requirements.

The service provided has developed through a process of feed-back between NERSC and us over several years, accordingly our technical requirements have been gradually meet and improved as well as we have been made aware of the limitations.

Validation - FD

1. Is the SPVR clear and user friendly?

This reports gives a qualitative assessment of the service and products performance in 2006. As NERSC indicates the individual products could have been validated more extensively against other observations, however the examples given illustrates that this service and products provided are fit for our use on early warning and monitoring.

2. Are the validation results clearly illustrated?

As examples they meet our requirement for validation, in addition to our own day to day assessment of the information, which are included in the weekly reports posted the AlgeInfo bulletin board (<http://algeinfo.imr.no>).

3. Is the service compliant with the Service Level Agreements?

YES, and even additional type and volume of information products are provided.

4. Is the service fit for purpose?

Definitely, YES for our purpose of early warning and monitoring of algae blooms in coastal Norwegian waters.

5. Is the product quality compliant with the specifications and user requirements?

YES as expected.

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6. (Optional) General comments regarding validation activities.

The MarCoast service provides us with an overview of what start in or enters the Norwegian waters. Through international cooperation (Sweden and Denmark), the regular Norwegian monitoring and identification of events, we have less requirements to quantitative observations than we would have had without this auxiliary information.

The data from NERSC are being used to initiate dedicated observations and field measurements in both areas and times that are not a part of the regular observational network. Tailored products can be useful during local bloom events in fjord, e.g better spatial resolution.

In summary: We generally observe a high correlation between our observations and the satellite data, particularly during high biomass algae blooms.

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USER QUESTIONNAIRE; NORWEGIAN SEAFOOD FEDERATION (FHL) - AQUACULTURE

This questionnaire is completed by Research Director Kjell Maroni, FHL Aquaculture.

User requirements - FHL

1. Does the end-user have effective access to the delivered information?

The end-users as aquaculture companies have relatively effective access to the information through our web-page www.fhl.no, but most need more detailed info as only the major algal blooms relatively seldom is of importance to the industry.

2. Is there effective communication between service provider and end-user including effective feedback mechanisms?

Have no experience with this, except for putting up the service through the web-page which works OK (but would like to receive an email warning when the server is out of function etc).

3. Is the presentation of information effective and suitable to the end user requirements?

More detailed info re bloom of minor algae not visible from satellite is often needed, especially for the shellfish growers.

4. What user needs does the service meet/not meet?

Meet an early warning need when new blooms might occur, but only for the major algae and tells nothing about minor, important species which might cause troubles.

5. To which international policies and regional directives, treaties and agreements does the services product(s) refer?

See answer from Directorate of Fisheries.

6. Does the service provide useful information for monitoring and assessing the state of the marine environment? Is there an added value brought by the service (i.e. is there a benefit or not – e. g. cost reduction, spatial/temporal coverage).

See no direct cost reduction for the end users, except if the service enables the end users to reduce mortality or quality problems due to blooms.

7. (Optional) General comments regarding user requirements.

Technical requirements - FHL

1. Does the service provide timely, reliable, and relevant information?

Yes, at the level of scale agreed upon.

2. What are the shortcomings and how often do they occur?

A few failures in delivery of the service recorded, at the moment not working properly, but do not know how often this occurs as we are not checking the service every day.

3. Are the shortcomings of the service explained?

Yes, normally an explanation is shown on the web-page.

4. Are uncertainties in the service products addressed in the documentation?

Yes.

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5. *Are the conditions under which the service is provided clearly identified?*

Yes.

6. *Are the service products documented in a complete and transparent manner?*

Yes.

7. *Is the product format and volume compliant with the specifications?*

Yes.

8. *Are the service's spatial (geographical) and temporal boundaries clearly defined?*

Yes, but we miss coverage over all Norway.

9. *(Optional) Does the service make use of appropriate local/regional information which may improve the final product(s)?*

We have not looked too much into this, but it would be nice if the service could be combined with existing information showing where different aquaculture sites in operation is located.

10. *(Optional) Have the algorithms been tuned to local conditions (where necessary)?*

11. *(Optional) Are the quality control procedures (e.g. flags) used appropriately?*

12. *(Optional) Have conservative assumptions been used?*

13. *Did any cases of disruption or temporary service non-compliance occur? If yes, how often?*

We have registered a few situations with technical disruption, explained in this report.

14. *What are the user risks related to disruption or temporary service non-compliance?*

Not very critical, as other info bases is also available to help out (e.g. <http://algeinfo.imr.no>), but in a situation with a detectable (from satellite) critical bloom disruption might be negative. Also to the degree the service covers oil spill spreading etc. a disruption would be negative.

15. *Is the authority and responsibility of the service delivery management clearly described?*

See answer form Directorate of Fisheries

16. *(Optional) Does the service require extensive initial training efforts in order to work as presumed during the service delivery period?*

No, but some aquaculture operations might need help to update their computers to a standard reading the format of the info (most will have no problems).

17. *(Optional) Does the service make provisions for meeting training needs?*

Not towards end users as single aquaculture operations, but to a certain extent this can be taken care of through FHL meeting with members.

18. *(Optional) Is a mechanism in place to assess the impact of the training and promotion activities?*

19. *(Optional) Are procedures identified to rapidly alert authorities in emergency situations?*

20. *(Optional) General comments regarding technical requirements.*

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Validation - FHL

1. *Is the SPVR clear and user friendly?*

Yes.

2. *Are the validation results clearly illustrated?*

Fairly clearly, but would also have been good to have some more evaluation about the limiting factors for detection of “minor” blooms of danger to the aquaculture industry (bloom not directly observed from satellite).

3. *Is the service compliant with the Service Level Agreements?*

Yes, and more service has been produced.

4. *Is the service fit for purpose?*

Yes, as commented relative to the MarCoast purpose, but not fully to the needs of the aquaculture industry when it comes to info about danger for HAB's.

5. *Is the product quality compliant with the specifications and user requirements?*

Yes.

6. *(Optional) General comments regarding validation activities.*

More focus on validation / testing if also minor species blooms can be detected / warned / forecasted would have been interesting, and also more focus on fjord/inshore service.

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Annex 1

Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing
Center (NERSC)
Thormøhlensgate 12

5006 BERGEN

Norway
Att: Lasse Pettersson

Inquiries to: Helen Christiansen

Telephone: 55 23 82 98

Division: The Coastal Management Section

Our reference: 04/9718

Your reference:

Our date: 12.12.2006

Your date:

Statement to NERSC

The Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries has over the years made use of the Nansen Environmental Remote Sensing Center (NERSC), which supplies a satellite picture service. This has been an exchange, where the interaction consists of the Directorate frequently receiving algae/-chlorophyll maps in the summer months, from the British Channel to Trøndelag in Norway, and the NERSC receives, in return, a professional comment and interpretation from us.

The satellite maps which amongst other show the level of chlorophyll in the sea, is a function of algae concentration. This is a very important tool when forming a total picture of potential algae blooms, where one weights the concerns on unwanted, harmful or toxic algae. Such algae blooms, can in some years, do plenty harm to wild fish and farmed fish. It is especially precarious for farmed fish, since they have no opportunity to escape such stress. This can result in fish death. It has been especially *Chattonella*, *Prymnesium* and *Chrysochromulina*, which have caused fish death in a variable degree in the years after 1988 (the time from when we began to register such accounts).

The Directorate of Fisheries has a contingency plan for crisis management in the coastal zone. Algae contingency is one of the most important objects of crisis. Updated satellite maps, showing the chlorophyll distribution in our oceans, will help us to limit contingency and monitoring efforts, hence gathering water samples after a rational and effective plan, within a relevant area of influence. This results in that the degree of coincidence is reduced with the expenses entailed on for the industry and the fisheries administration.

On the Directorate of Fisheries' website, www.fiskeridir.no, one can find in the bottom right corner a satellite map transferred from NERSC. By clicking on the map one accesses the Directorate of Fisheries contingency portal, www.fiskeridir.no/beredskapsportalen. On this page both our own local and regional offices, participants in fishery trade, other relevant governmental departments and joint venture partners, and not to mention the general public will

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find routines for handling different crisis objects together with links to relevant literature.

The NERSC are competent in both ocean and environmental monitoring, and are a very important link in the Directorate of Fisheries' contingency work in the coastal zone.

This was also manifested through the following agreement: "MarCoast – Marine and Coastal Services, a Service Level Agreement between the Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center and the Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries". This agreement was signed the 30.03.2005.

To conclude we would like to direct your attention to our motto "Life in the sea – our joint responsibility!"

Yours sincerely

Ragnar Sandbæk
Head of Section

Helen Christiansen
Advisor

END OF DOCUMENT

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